

PROFESSIONAL STANDARD OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION TEACHERS: COMPONENT ANALYSIS AND PROFESSIONAL REQUIREMENTS

A.A. Ibragimov¹, G.Sh. Fayzullaeva²

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor, Vice-Rector of Samarkand International Technological University¹

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Primary and Preschool Education Methodology, Samarkand State Pedagogical Institute²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18466831>

Abstract. *The professional standard for secondary school teachers is a set of requirements aimed at enhancing the quality of education, continuously developing teachers' professional competencies and ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process. This article analytically examines the methodological foundations of the professional standard for general secondary education teachers, the sections and areas included in the standard, as well as the system of criteria for professional activities. Moreover, the mechanisms by which the professional standard influences students' educational outcomes and its practical significance are elucidated. The indicators defined for certain areas of the standard are interpreted based on the author's explanations, and suggestions and recommendations for their effective application in educational practice are presented.*

Keywords: *teacher, standard, field, criterion, indicator, quality of education, professional competence, pedagogical process.*

INTRODUCTION. The growing societal demand for competitive personnel is creating conditions for the globalization of education. This, in turn, is leading to an increase in the workload and responsibilities placed on teachers. Such a situation necessitates not only the effective organization of pedagogical staff activities but also the need for independent professional development and continuous improvement of their competence level. In many developed countries, including our republic, the professional standard of a secondary school teacher (hereinafter - the professional standard) is a regulatory document introduced into practice as a basis for regulating the professional activity of a teacher in order to create a trajectory of professional development and correctly program their actions in this direction.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Professional standards are formed based on classification units and requirements that reflect social demand. Currently, countries worldwide are developing National Qualification Frameworks based on the "International Standard Classification of Education" (ISCED) [3]. This document eliminates the problematic situations that arise in the comparative assessment of achievements and the study of progress towards international goals due to the diversity of educational systems and programs of different countries. ISCED - adopted at the 36th session of the UNESCO General Conference in November 2011, is a conceptual document on the correct interpretation of the process occurring in education systems and its important aspects on a global scale, the classification and presentation of internationally comparable data.

The legal conceptual foundations for improving the spheres of education and science in our country, further strengthening respect for teachers and pedagogical workers in our society, promoting the development of their professional skills, in particular, assessing the results achieved by teachers with specific criteria, and organizing the activities of the national system in this regard are fully reflected in the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 15, 2020 No. 287 “On Measures to Organize the Activities of the National System for the Development of Professional Qualifications, Knowledge and Skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan” [2].

A professional standard is a standard that reflects the main labor functions and the conditions for their performance, defines the requirements for the level of skill, the content, quality, and conditions of labor, and serves as the main driving criterion in education. The professional standard of a teacher in Uzbekistan was developed by a working group of the Abdulla Avloni Research Institute for the Study of Problems and Forecasting the Prospects of Public Education with the support of the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) in Uzbekistan [4]. The experience of different countries was studied and international experts were involved in the development of the standard, extensive discussions were held among specialists in the field of education, and consultations were held with practical teachers. The professional standard is a document of a certain scope that reflects and defines the set of knowledge, skills, and personal qualities necessary for the formation of competencies of a modern teacher [1, 6, 8]. Based on the objective of our research, which focuses on the practical application of professional standards, we deemed it necessary to thoroughly examine the content of the areas covered by the newly implemented professional standard, analyze the tasks defined within it, and discuss its expected outcomes in detail.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION. Consequently, the framework of the professional standard of competencies of a teacher-teacher of a general education school has a specific structure and consists of such components as sections, the main goal of the type of activity, areas of competence or labor function, standards of competencies, indicators of the teacher's activity/labor actions. In particular, the 1st section, entitled "General Information", provides the types of activities [4], and in the methodological manual, which is presented as the main source for communicating the professional standard to teachers (as well as in the attached “Professional Standard”), the concepts of sections and related “labor tasks” are enriched with such concepts as “competence standard” and “field”. For example, analysis of the first section, titled “The Structure of Professional Standards: Social and Professional Competencies of Teachers”, which presents general information, reveals that it was developed based on a competency-based approach, and each requirement for teachers is aimed at expanding the scope of competencies [6]. Additionally, the use of concepts such as field, standard indicators, or competencies in the standard classification presented in the text is based on the document “Professional Standard for General Secondary School Teachers” appended to the manual.

According to its content, Section 2 of the professional standard defines the requirements for a teacher's social and professional competencies (job responsibilities), as well as the set of values they must adhere to in their professional activities. The document structure consists of professional competencies, professional knowledge, practical skills, and correspondingly: 7 areas of professional competencies, while Section 3 comprises 19 standards that represent their expansion, along with 65 indicators of work actions.

At this point, let us dwell a little on the social competencies and values of a teacher, because it is these qualities that guarantee their adaptation, readiness, and sense of responsibility to the requirements and obligations of learning and teaching in the constantly changing conditions of the 21st century.

In particular, the possession of skills, abilities to be active in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activity [5] are social competencies in the individual, which, in our opinion, in relation to the activity of a teacher implies:

- ✓ the possibility of establishing relationships between all subjects of the educational process;

- ✓ the ability to create an atmosphere of interpersonal communication in various emotional states, communicativeness at the level of conflict resolution;

- ✓ validity in demonstrating one's civic position and using all possibilities in its formation in students;

- ✓ eloquence, correct use of the native language, etiquette, and cultural expression of opinions;

- ✓ the ability to understand local solidarity and collective unity among colleagues and students, and the capacity to implement cooperation for working in groups;

- ✓ dedication to consciously defining one's attitude towards educational goals and pedagogical, psychological, and methodological factors, encouraging the improvement of the quality of the school process through the method of positively influencing others in their activities.

The strengthening of social competence in a teacher is accompanied by the manifestation of values [8; p. 78] and values in the teacher differ in that they are oriented towards the student, possess personal and professional skills, and are a member of the school community.

- firstly, respect the dignity, personality, rights, freedoms, and emotions of students, regardless of their origin, religion, race, and social status. Ensure their expression as independent individuals, believe in their potential for development and success, recognize their individuality, and perceive the world, thoughts, and values from their perspective.

- secondly, adherence to universal and peculiar to the teaching profession principles, orientation towards the highest quality, activity in continuous improvement, innovation, integrability, adaptability to changes, analysis of acquired experience and introduction of innovations and changes into professional practice, understanding and approval of cultural diversity, justice and objectivity;

- thirdly, cooperation, jointly solving professional problems, responsibility for the educational, upbringing, and organizational development of the school, and having a place in the life of the school and the local community.

A broad coverage of the essence of the professional standard will become the basis for many studies on the professional development of teachers, and in this work, based on the topic, goals, and objectives of the conducted research, the 2nd section and the 6th section of the 3rd section of the professional standard are covered in more detail.

The second section is called "Management of the Educational and Upbringing Process" and covers five areas shown in the figure above [4].

First sphere. Planning the educational process - the teacher plans activities in this area within the framework of state educational standards and the curriculum; competence standards for the teacher's development of an educational and methodological complex (curriculum, lesson

plans, notes, didactic and handouts) in accordance with the curriculum and performance indicators/work actions related to each of them are defined:

- for a teacher to plan activities within the framework of state educational standards and curriculum, the following labor actions are necessary: - Develop curricula in accordance with the objectives of state educational standards and educational programs; adapt curricula based on students' needs and interests (if necessary); - Implement planning of their activities based on the principles of interdisciplinary correlation and integration;

- when developing an educational and methodological complex (lesson plan, notes, didactic materials) in accordance with the curriculum, the teacher: develops a lesson plan, taking into account the data obtained as a result of assessing students' knowledge, defining clear and measurable goals and results of the lesson; plans lesson forms and methods corresponding to the goals of the lesson, age characteristics and assimilation of students, the use of relevant educational, demonstration and handout materials; plans the integration of modern information technologies into the lesson process.

It is not by chance that the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System until 2030 highlights among the urgent tasks for teachers “mastering modern theories of teaching, understanding pedagogical psychology, and acquiring competency-based and personality-oriented approaches to education” and “creating modern forms of strategic planning in public education management, expanding the practice of utilizing innovative ideas, developments and technologies, and advanced achievements based on international experience in the field” [1].

Planning is a set of forms of regulation and management of socio-economic processes at various levels of the national economy [7; P. 370]. Based on this definition, planning is the most important professional competence of a teacher, relating to the entire activity of the teacher, which is the basis for the successful manifestation of other areas of competence. It is important not only for the orderly conduct of the educational process, but also in the personal and professional factors of self-development.

The teacher's methodological competence manifests itself in the planning of the educational process. The calendar-thematic plan for subjects is compiled and approved by authorized organizations, which means that the teacher knows the main goal and objectives of the plan, which is a good source for the teacher to plan the subject in detail. In particular, it is not enough to know the time distribution of topics for effective planning of one's activities in the educational process. Applying this procedure in various forms and types of lessons, and most importantly, clarifying the educational goal of each topic in the subject, defining tasks, correctly choosing necessary methods, and preparing answers to questions such as which life competencies the studied topic helps to form in the student, its relevance, and ability to apply it in practice, are reflected in the teacher's correct planning of the content delivery process and lesson time. Also, the creative ability to create a technological map reflecting the content of lesson minutes on each topic, the gradual concrete development of assessment rubrics based on the essence of the tasks, ensuring an integrative approach in the unity of theory and practice confirm that the teacher has fulfilled the indicators of activity in this area of competence.

Second sphere. Sphere 2 of Section 2 of the Professional Standard is called "Ensuring the Effectiveness of Education (Implementation of Educational Programs) " [4]. Competency requirements in this area are a continuation, a complement to the 1st area analyzed above, that is, the correct execution of planning is explained by its successful application in the process.

In order for the teacher to effectively organize the educational process, it is necessary to convey to students the tasks set in achieving the educational goal defined in the planning, to explain which of its requirements it meets when performing these tasks, which plays a leading role in the assessment. For example, if the lesson is designed to cover a new topic, there will be a short lecture and a corresponding test, or group work will be organized, aimed at the independent assimilation of new content by students. In general, section 2 of the standard can be analyzed in the author's interpretation in the table as follows (Table 1):

Table 1.

Analysis of sphere 2 of the Professional Standard of a Teacher of a General Secondary School

Sphere 2	Ensuring the effectiveness of education (implementation of educational programs)
2.1. Content of standard and indicators	<i>The teacher effectively organizes the learning process.</i>
	<i>Defines achievable tasks for students based on the lesson objectives:</i>
	- at the beginning of the lesson, the lesson objective is conveyed in a clear, simple, and fluent manner;
	- explains the assessment system;
	- familiarizes with the sequence and essence of the tasks to be performed;
	- determines how the explanations during the lesson have influenced the students to create a working environment.
	<i>Use demonstration and handout materials relevant to the lesson topic:</i>
	- prepares visual and handout materials according to the learning objective and type of lesson;
	- ensures the correspondence of exhibition materials to all elements of the lesson: topic, goal, task, activity and assessment, educational aspect to the national mentality;
	- plans the content to correspond to the age and individual characteristics of the student;
	- ensures that the demonstration material is clearly visible and that the student's attention is focused on the visual aids.
	<i>Spends time wisely in class:</i>
	- a logical algorithm of the lesson is created, that is, a flexible, systematic plan;
	- takes into account the level of preparedness, potential, independence of students in the distribution of time, a detailed description of each step of the lesson;
	- monitors and further improves the plan's execution rate in practice.
	<i>Use ICT to support the educational process and solve educational problems:</i>
- develops their technological competence and forms digital competencies in students;	
- organizes the lesson using ICT at times appropriate for the student's age characteristics (compliant with SanPin requirements).	

	<p><i>Based on the knowledge obtained as a result of assessing students' knowledge, they analyze the effectiveness of their approaches to organizing lessons and teaching.</i></p>
<p>2.2. Content of standard and indicators</p>	<p><i>The teacher selects and applies teaching methods and approaches that correspond to the learning objectives and the age characteristics of the students.</i></p> <p><i>Utilizes active learning methods (frontal learning cannot be dominant):</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - directs activating methods towards an educational goal; - allows finding solutions to situations, grouping, searching, independent work, studying the problem, reading in the process, asking questions, discussing, searching for information; - manages time correctly. <p><i>Uses methods aimed at developing the basic competencies and life skills of students, defined in the educational standards of general secondary education:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - forms basic competencies and life skills in students through elements and tools intended for development through various teaching methods (for example: problem-based, project-based, personality-based, process-based, result-based learning). <p><i>Organizes the collective and project work of students:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher takes a project-based training coaching course; - teaches students to work together on projects in groups and systematizes teaching methods based on problem-based, research-based, and exploratory approaches. <p><i>Utilizes various approaches to teaching students metacognitive strategy, including planning, control, and self-assessment skills:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - teaches cognitive strategies such as goal-setting, result setting, critical thinking, creativity, comparison, understanding, prediction, creating an algorithm of intermediate steps, reflection, which ensure the independent performance of educational activities.
<p>2.3. Content of standard and indicators</p>	<p><i>The teacher actively involves students in the process, creating motivation for learning.</i></p> <p><i>Provides timely differentiated assistance to students based on their individual learning needs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher effectively uses elements and tools of personality-based learning in their lessons.

	- studies the interests and needs of the class, using methods such as creating corresponding differentiated tasks.
	<i>Shows the connection of the lesson topic with practice (using real-life examples):</i>
	- the teacher constantly connects theory with practice, instilling in the student that school subjects are subjects that teach life;
	- Forms a clear answer to the question of why each subject is necessary in life, teaches students to use the surrounding reality as a source of knowledge.
	<i>During the lesson, each student is given the opportunity to express their ideas and views:</i>
	- creates an atmosphere in the classroom that ensures collaboration, teaches creativity through guiding questions;
	- develops the student's communicative competence through various situations of direct and indirect communication.
	<i>Students use their personal interests to motivate their active participation in the lesson.</i>
	<i>Utilizes various methods to engage students in the lesson:</i>
	- uses all methods aimed at increasing student motivation and creates a psychological environment that fosters confidence, patience, security, freedom, and responsibility in the educational process.
	<i>Provides effective classroom communication:</i>
	- the teacher serves as an example for developing competence and communication culture in students.

It was deemed necessary to explain it in more detail with the conclusion that the above-mentioned second sphere of the standard manifests itself as a result of self-development in the teacher's activity.

Third sphere. Sphere 3 of Section 2 is titled “Assessment of Learning and Provision of Feedback” [4]. This section encompasses competency standards and ten performance indicators/work actions, including: the teacher’s knowledge and application of modern theories; regular evaluation and analysis of students’ educational achievements by the teacher; provision of information to students about their achievements, motivating them to continue learning and developing; observation and description of difficulties students face in learning, and consultation with a specialist in the relevant field when necessary.

In fact, there are diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment methods, which manifest themselves in several ways depending on the form and characteristics, the nature of the expression. When conducting any type of assessment, it is important that its criteria are clear and understandable, or that the teacher constantly performs actions to explain the rubrics of assessment, since assessment determines assimilation, stabilizes the student's motivation, and creates feedback. It helps to eliminate shortcomings and increase achievements.

Fourth sphere. The 4th sphere of the professional standard is called “Organization of Educational Activities”, which contains two competency standards: “The teacher organizes educational activities in various forms that contribute to the development of students and the

formation of social norms” and “The teacher conducts educational activities by developing values and using interactive forms and methods of educational work” [4].

This field requires teachers not only to master their subject, but also to identify students' educational needs, develop their emotional and value spheres, teach etiquette rules, effectively organize play, educational research, and leisure time, apply modern interactive methods of educational work, consider students' religion, gender, age, cultural and individual characteristics, train students in volunteering, possess psychological knowledge for conflict situations, create a positive environment, and foster tolerance, patience, determination, moral norms, and life preparation skills in students through their own example of tolerance. Additionally, teachers must develop students' cognitive activity, independence, initiative, creativity, civic position, work capacity, and a culture of healthy and safe lifestyle.

Fifth sphere. This is the final sphere of Section 2 and is titled “Creating and Ensuring a Safe Developmental Educational Environment” [4]. In this context, the teacher's social, psychological, innovative, and integrative competencies play a crucial role. This area encompasses competency standards such as “The teacher creates a psychologically and physically safe environment for all students”, “The educator effectively manages the classroom and adapts the educational environment to meet students' needs”, and “The educator fosters civic competencies and media literacy in students”.

Based on the brief definitions of the content of the standards of this field, it is emphasized that the teacher must create a chain of love and trust for the student in the classroom, an inclusive educational environment based on the possibility of equality, regardless of gender, nationality, language, religion, social status, or special needs, resolve conflict situations, as well as explain to himself the essence of observing safety rules, manage the classroom with the accuracy of the need, individualize education, ensure compliance by students with the rules of ethics, form civic competencies and develop a culture of using the media.

The third section of the professional standard is called "Professional Development and Cooperation" and represents two areas within the duration of the standard content (Table 2).

Table 2.

Analysis of Sphere 6 of the Professional Standard of a Teacher of a General Secondary School

Sphere 6	Self-development and professional growth
6.1. Content of standard and indicators	<i>The teacher understands the importance of learning throughout life and uses various opportunities for professional development.</i>
	<i>Undergoes regular professional development courses:</i>
	- study in a continuing professional development course in offline and online form and receive a corresponding certificate;
	- feels the obligation to improve their professional level;
	- receives training in short and long-term courses devoted to innovations in science and current problems.
	<i>Participates in seminars and trainings, as well as other events aimed at ensuring professional development:</i>
	- selects trainings aimed at developing professional competencies in accordance with their needs;
- reflection on modern trends, professional standards, awareness of	

	<p>the level of professional qualifications.</p> <p><i>Participates in the school's "methodological councils," the purpose of which is to improve work and exchange experience:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - directly participates in the work of the methodological association and the methodological council; - develops their professional competencies, provides methodological assistance to a colleague; - performs methodological work in collaboration within a methodological association, creating various methods, tools, forms, and criteria.
6.2. Content of standard and indicators	<p><i>The teacher works together with colleagues to exchange experience and improve their professional skills.</i></p> <p><i>Attends mutual lessons, analyzes them, uses them in their professional activities:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher observes the lessons of his colleague so that he can draw conclusions related to his practice; - is active in the "mentor-student" tradition at school, studies and applies in practice the skills of teachers with high experience; - provides feedback that allows for improved learning practice.
	<p><i>Prepares and conducts open lessons to demonstrate their experience:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher prepares for the open lesson theoretically, practically, methodologically, psychologically, as well as for discussions (critical thinking) after the open lesson and the reception of expressed opinions;
	<p>After the lesson, they explain their objective and the logical sequence of teaching methods to their colleagues.</p>
	<p><i>The teacher plans and implements their professional development based on self-analysis and self-assessment of their work.</i></p> <p><i>Constantly familiarizes themselves with scientific literature and applies new knowledge in practice:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher studies scientific, methodological, and other literature related to their subject, selects and analyzes reliable sources, familiarizes themselves with modern teaching theory and new trends; - processes the information received, applies the best practices, software, and methodological innovations learned in their practice, and draws appropriate conclusions; - based on the need to organize today's educational environment in interdisciplinary integration, it is used in daily activities to increase the effectiveness of educational outcomes.
	<p><i>Constantly familiarizes themselves with scientific literature and applies new knowledge in practice:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the teacher studies scientific, methodological, and other literature related to their subject, selects and analyzes reliable sources, familiarizes themselves with modern teaching theory and new trends;
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - processes the information received, applies the best practices, software, and methodological innovations learned in their practice, and draws appropriate conclusions;
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - based on the need to organize today's educational environment in interdisciplinary integration, it is used in daily activities to increase the effectiveness of educational outcomes.

	<i>Adequately assesses their educational activities (strengths and weaknesses) and can identify the needs for professional development:</i>
	- the teacher regularly identifies the causes of professional difficulties through self-diagnosis;
	- conducts self-analysis according to the requirements of the teacher's professional standards, searches for self-assessment maps, and diagnoses interactions with students.
	<i>Draws up a plan for independent study and, after its implementation, a report:</i>
	- Taking into account the importance of having an independent educational plan for each teacher, creates their own individual trajectory of personal and professional development;
	- ensures the alignment of the plan with its direction and activity, clearly defines the goal, objectives, and correspondingly the expected results, and constructs algorithmic actions of various forms of self-improvement.
	<i>Carries out the necessary changes in their work practice:</i>
	- during each lesson, the teacher searches for ways to form feedback with students, their reflection, monitors their lesson and the level of its impact on students;
	- introduces changes to the methods of motivating students based on the study of their constant experience, analysis of their own results; uses various forms of working with them (working in small groups, pairs, etc.);
	- develops various rubrics aimed at formative assessment of students, introduces the self-assessment process into student discussion.

Since this area of competence “Self-development and professional growth” represents the main content and direction for the practical application of the professional standard defined in our study, we tried to interpret and respond to it more broadly.

Seventh sphere. The 7th sphere of the professional standard is titled “Collaboration with colleagues and parents (or their substitutes) of students” [4]. Specifically, it presents competency standards such as “The teacher engages parents in various forms of cooperation with the school for the benefit of children's development” and “The teacher collaborates with colleagues and specialists to accomplish educational and upbringing tasks”. Additionally, it outlines performance indicators and work activities including: involving students' parents (or their substitutes) in the educational process, classroom and school life; designing and implementing the student's individual educational trajectory in cooperation with relevant specialists to achieve results; and collaborating with other pedagogical staff, specialists, and public organizations to address educational challenges in preparing students for life.

CONCLUSION. Each labor function defined in the professional standard, labor actions, necessary skills, necessary knowledge, and other characteristics constitute a characteristic with

specific meaning and content. In conclusion, the implementation of the professional standard and its effectiveness depend on the degree to which the established competencies are manifested in the teacher's professional activity. In this process, a teacher must not only integrate their existing knowledge, skills, experience, and practice, but also acquire the necessary skills to meet the requirements of professional standards.

REFERENCES

1. Amrilloevich, I. A. Comparative Analysis of Foreign Experiences in the Development of Professional Standards of Teachers. *JournalNX*, 785-787.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030." National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, April 29, 2019, No. 06/19/5712/3034.
3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 287 dated May 15, 2020, "On Measures to Organize the Functioning of the National System for the Development of Professional Qualifications, Knowledge and Skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan." National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, May 16, 2020, No. 09/20/287/0595.
4. International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 2011). UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS), P.O. Box 6128, Succursale Centre-Ville, Montreal, Quebec H3C 3J7, Canada, 2013, 89 p.
5. Occupational Standard for General Secondary School Teachers. Order of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 43-IC dated February 8, 2021 (registered under No. R.003.043.0964/B-21).
6. Muslimov, N. A., et al. Technology for Developing Professional Competence of Vocational Education Teachers. Monograph. Tashkent: Fan va Texnologiya Publishing House, 2013.
7. Application of the Professional Standard in the Activities of General Secondary School Teachers. Methodological Guide for Teachers and Methodologists. Collective of authors. Tashkent, 2022, 131 p.
8. Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language. Vol. 3. Editorial Board: T. Mirzayev et al.; Institute of Language and Literature, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", 2006, 688 p.
9. Fayzullaeva, G. (2024). THE FACTORS OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS. *Science and innovation*, 3(B3), 376-381.
10. Fomenko, S. L. Scientific and Methodological Support for the Formation of a Pedagogical Collective as a Subject of Implementing the Competence-Based Model of Education: Theory and Practice. Moscow: "APK i PPRO" Publishing House, 2011, 246 p.